

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE
ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART XI.
VELOCITY OF REPLACEMENT OF THE CHLORINE ATOMS
IN THE CHLORO DERIVATIVES OF THE SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF ACETOACETIC ACID

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Chemical activity of the substances mentioned below as expressed by the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atom has been correlated with their absorption spectra: (1) monochloroacetoacetanilide, (2) monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide, (3) monochloroacetoacet-*a*-naphthylamide.

Results indicate that the following factors influence the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atom by hydrogen: (i) the position as well as the spatial arrangement of the radicals like the methyl groups in the nuclear rings attached to the carbonyl groups of these groups; (ii) the unsymmetry of the group round the central carbon, resulting into unbalanced unilateral tension. The replacement of chlorine increases in rapidity as we pass from monochloroacetoacetanilide, through monochloroaceto-1:3:4-xylylamide to monochloroacetoacet-*a*-naphthylamide, it being the most rapid in the last case.

These investigations have been undertaken with a view to see if the velocity of replacement of chlorine in compounds such as (1) monochloroacetoacetanilide, (2) monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide and (3) monochloroacetoacet-*a*-naphthylamide, is correlated with the nature and position of the groups attached to the carbonyl radicals having -CHCl- complex in between. It is possible that the activity of the chlorine atom, thus situated in the molecule, may be influenced by the same factors which govern the lability of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group (-CH₂-) situated between two carbonyl groups in the case of the amide derivatives of acetoacetic acid; and this phase of the activity of molecules may be correlated with their absorption in the ultraviolet.

The velocity of replacement of chlorine atom has been studied on the basis of the reduction of chlorine atom in the molecule by means of hydrogen iodide. This is brought about by treating the chloro compound by means of hydriodic acid generated by the action of hydrochloric acid and potassium iodide (Kurt and Meyer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 951, 305).

The method used for the determination of the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atom by hydrogen, can be outlined as follows.

The substance (0.001 g.-mol.) was dissolved in 98% alcohol and the volume was made up to 100 c.c. so as to have an ultimate concentration of 0.01 g.-mol. per litre. In a wide-mouthed glass-stoppered bottle 5 c.c. of the above solution were run in with the help of a burette. Consecutively 5 c.c. of 0.5 *N*-HCl and 0.5 *N*-KI solution were also run in the same bottle. Eight such bottles were placed simultaneously at a known time in an electrically regulated thermostat, maintained at 35°. At suitable intervals of 1, 3, 5, 10, 25, 45, 70 and 100 minutes, one bottle at a time was removed from the thermostat and 50 c.c. of ice-cold water were added to the reacting mixture in order to arrest the reaction. The iodine liberated during the reaction, was then titrated immediately with 0.01*N*-sodium thiosulphate using 1 c.c. of 1% starch-solution.

Simultaneously with the above set of experiments, an equal number of bottles containing the reacting mixture without the chloro compound was placed in the thermostat for a blank check.

The results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1.

Time interval in minutes.	Percentage reduced of		
	Monochloroacetoacetanilide.	Monochloro acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide.	Monochloroacetoacet- α -naphthylamide.
1	7'25	22'50	24'50
3	25'25	36'50	55'00
5	40'00	55'00	77'65
10	60'00	73'00	89'75
25	90'75	88'75	95'00
45	97'25	91'50	97'00
70	97'75	91'75	98'00
100	98'00	92'00	99'00

In Fig. 1 are drawn the curves for the velocity of reduction of the chlorine atom in the compounds (1) monochloroacetoacetanilide, (2) monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide and (3) monochloroacetoacet- α -naphthylamide.

FIG. 1

It will be seen that the relative position and disposition of the velocity curves (1) and (2) are in good accord with those of the absorption curves of these substances.

Moreover, it appears that the percentage of the substance reduced in 100 minutes is higher in the case of monochloroacetoacet- α -naphthylamide. In the case of this compound,

the valency-bond represented by the arrow may appropriate a large amount of the total force of valency of the central carbon atom, with the consequence that a small amount of the valency force is left over to keep attached the chlorine atom and so it becomes readily reduced.

It will also be seen from the table and the curves plotted, that at the start, replacement of chlorine is peculiarly rapid and increases in rapidity as we pass from monochloroacetoacetanilide through monochloroacetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide to monochloroacetoacet- α -naphthylamide, it being the most rapid in the case of the last one.

From these observations, it can be assumed that this peculiar behaviour may be attributed to the influence of the other groups attached to the carbon atom, to which also the chlorine atom is linked, as also to the influence of the methyl groups present in the nucleus.

Further, in this case, the behaviour exhibited by these substances, can be attributed to the following factors which are supposed to influence the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atom by hydrogen :—

1. The position of the radicals like the methyl groups, in the nuclear rings attached to the carbonyl groups, as well as the spatial arrangement of these groups.
2. The unsymmetry of the group round the central carbon, resulting into an unbalanced unilateral tension.

It will be interesting here to refer to the results of a similar work carried out in this laboratory, in connection with the replacement of the chlorine atom, in compounds such as, $\text{ClHC}(\text{CONHR})_2$, $\text{Cl}_2\text{C}(\text{CONHR})_2$ (Mehta, M.Sc. Thesis, 1939. Bomb. Univ.).

From reference to the results (obtained by Naik, Trivedi and Mehta, Part II, of this series, this Journal, 1943, 20, 355), it will be seen that Pichloromalondi-1:3:4-xylylamide is not reduced at all. This has been explained on the basis that symmetry round the central carbon atom makes the whole molecule more stable with the consequence of non-reducibility of the chlorine atoms under experimental conditions. It is quite apparent from the results that as soon as the symmetry is disturbed, the reactivity of the molecule appears to be enhanced, as expressed by the velocity of reduction of the chlorine atom in the corresponding monochloromalon-di-1:3:4-xylylamide, which is in accordance with the results obtained by measuring the velocity of hydrolysis of this class of compounds.

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